

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF FRICTIONAL BEHAVIOR AND HEAT TRANSFER IN 3D PRINTED ROCKET ENGINE COOLING CHANNELS

T. Santese ⁽¹⁾, A. Söndgerath ⁽²⁾, S. Soller ⁽²⁾, B. Latini ⁽³⁾, C. Manfletti ⁽¹⁾

⁽¹⁾ *Technical University of Munich, School of Engineering and Design, Department of Aerospace and Geodesy, Chair of Space Mobility and Propulsion, Germany*

⁽²⁾ *ArianeGroup GmbH, D82024 Taufkirchen, Germany*

⁽³⁾ *Sapienza University of Rome, Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Italy*

KEYWORDS: surface roughness, 3D printed, heat flux, cooling channels

ABSTRACT:

An experimental campaign has been conducted at the Space Propulsion Laboratory of Technical University of Munich (TUM) with the goal of characterizing pressure drop and heat transfer performances in new 3D printed segments of a thrust chamber. Four different specimens with different surface qualities in the combustion chamber and in the cooling channels have been tested, at real rocket engines operating conditions. CFD simulations of the cooling channels are performed in order to compare experimental data and numerical results through the use of RANS simulations and state-of-the-art roughness models. It has been found that the roughness in the cooling channels leads to an increment of the heat pick up of about the 10% while a rough chamber brings a more significant increase, up to the 30%. Pressure drops have also shown to be remarkably increased. RANS simulations are able to predict these results, however, proper tuning of the modelling parameters is required.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the last decades, the space sector has seen significant growth, and many nations have invested time and resources in new technologies to reduce the cost of access to space. Space agencies and companies aim to design, produce, and launch new and more efficient systems, implementing system simplifications (e.g. reducing the number of components) and new manufacturing methods as well as new functionalities, to significantly reduce the cost of production, and increase the production cadence of space hardware. However, these modifications and new functionalities must be researched and tested before becoming operative and qualified for space missions. One of the most known is the use of additive manufacturing (AM) techniques. These new production processes are associated with one major challenge, primarily due to the inherent high surface roughness that results. This roughness plays a crucial role in determining pressure losses and heat transfer. The

effectiveness of roughness removal technologies is often limited, especially when dealing with intricate and narrow channels as are typical of liquid rocket regenerative cooling systems. To harness metal AM for creating small flow channels, a comprehensive understanding of AM tolerances and surface roughness becomes imperative

Due to the relatively recent commercial availability of metal AM technologies, there is a limited corpus of public literature on this subject. The majority of research efforts aimed at characterizing this process have predominantly centred around its mechanical properties.

Numerous researchers have identified build orientation as a factor exerting a substantial influence on surface finish. Delgado et al. [7], investigating parts manufactured through DMLS (Direct Metal Laser Sintering) with an iron-based material, observed that roughness is influenced by layer thickness, scan speed, and build direction, with the latter having the most significant impact.

Ventola et al. [25] corroborated the substantial impact of build direction on surface roughness in DMLS. They noted a pronounced increase in roughness at angled build directions due to the inherent stair-stepping effect associated with layer-by-layer manufacturing processes. In the realm of fluid dynamics, surface roughness is an old topic, and the first remarkable results go back to the experiments of Nikuradse, [15], who was able to map the increased friction in the flow inside circular pipes with homogenous roughness. Jones, [9], scrutinized published data on flow in rectangular channels, challenging the adequacy of the equivalent or hydraulic diameter, D_h , in determining friction factors from pressure drop data. Proposing the use of a laminar equivalent diameter, D_L , based on the aspect ratio of the channel, Jones argued that this correction is crucial. Notably, Jones found that evaluating turbulent data with the corrected diameter significantly improved agreement with established correlations for turbulent pipe flow, such as the Colebrook equation. Literature reveals limited exploration of convective heat transfer in specimens manufactured through AM, with only a few studies addressing this aspect, [6, 25, 26]. The only investigations into the internal heat transfer of additively manufactured channels are the experiments carried out by Stimpson et al. [23, 24]

and, in the same research group, by Snyder et al. [22]. In these recent works, a test coupon is additively manufactured, and a flow of air is let inside the rectangular channels. The coupon is heated by an electrical heater, and the pressure and temperature are measured at the inlet and outlet. The authors were able to quantify the increase in the Nusselt number and in the friction factor and compare them with commonly used empirical laws for smooth surfaces. Additionally, the database created in their work, [23], has been the reference for many numerical investigations, in which new roughness models were tested and compared with the experimental results obtained in [23], with the aim of improving simulations results, [11–13]. However, these experiments were conducted at relatively low Reynolds number, not higher than 40.000. Furthermore, the heat flux provided by the electrical heater was not comparable to the one that is observed in rocket engine combustion chambers.

The experimental work conducted by the authors of this paper had therefore, the objective to quantify the pressure drop and the heat transfer pick-up in 3D printed segments, at operating conditions which resemble the ones in real high-thrust rocket engine combustion chambers. Four specimens have been tested which feature different surface finishes of the cooling channels and of the combustion chamber walls. The comparison is made possible by the modularity of the combustion chamber that is utilized: the new specimens are installed in the middle of the combustion chamber, substituting two previous segments, as will be better explained in the next section.

In addition, CFD simulations are used to compare the experimental data with numerically obtained results. These numerical models rely on recently developed surface roughness models. Some modifications are available, which are based on tuning the turbulent Prandtl number in the energy equation, [1]. Proper tuning of the turbulent Prandtl number is required to get satisfactory results, as shown in [10]. However, there is a scarcity of literature on the tuning of such quantities based on experimental data. Some of these studies include [12, 13, 23, 24], where the topic of the study is the effect of roughness on micro-channels at low Reynolds numbers. The work conducted by the authors of this paper will therefore enrich the literature on the relationship between rough surfaces and heat transfer.

This work is structured as follows: the second section provides an overview of the hardware used for the test campaign, as well as the main details about the test specimen; the third section presents the numerical setup used to run the simulations; and finally the fourth section is dedicated to the results and the comparison between numerical and experimental results, after the tuning of the parameters.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

2.1. Hardware

All the experiments have been performed at the Space Propulsion Laboratory in TUM. The test-bench is equipped to test with gaseous methane (CH₄) and gaseous oxygen (GOX) and reach combustion chamber pressures up to 80bar. The multi-element rocket combustion chamber used for this study, Fig.1, has a 30mm inner-diameter, a contraction ratio of 2.4 and an expansion ratio of 1.73.

Figure 1 TUM engine setup modifications.

The distance between injectors and the injector-wall distance are kept constant for easier scaling up or down of the design, resulting in a path of 6 elements evenly distributed in a circumference, and one element in its center. For simplicity, flush shear coaxial elements are used.

For more details on the injectors dimensions, see our previous works in [19–21]. In this paper, we present two configurations of the same chamber, which have been tested and compared. The first configuration, is the old setup of the chamber, which includes 4 segments (A-B-C-D) made of CuCrZr, preceded by an igniter ring and followed by a nozzle, for a total length of 375mm, see Fig.1. Two spark-plug igniters are placed in the igniter ring to ensure smooth and symmetric ignition procedure.

To test the new specimen, the segment B and C are substituted with one single segment (see segment R in Fig.1), which has the same length as the sum of the two previous segments. The 3D printed segment is cooled with gaseous nitrogen, splitting the chamber-water-circuit in two parts, as indicated in Fig.1 by the blue dashed line. The placement of the new specimen has been carefully decided based on the experience coming from the past: the

center position allows us to consider the combustion complete enough to assume the heat flux to be constant. Additionally, the segment “D” is kept between the segment “R” and the nozzle. This was done to thermally insulate the 3D printed specimen from the strong heat conduction with the nozzle, which is kept much colder to avoid any damage on the most solicited part, and preserve the quality of the temperature measurements.

The test specimens examined in this test campaign were cooled with a different cooling circuit which was fed by nitrogen at ambient temperature. Because of its relatively short length, gaseous nitrogen is chosen in order to maximize the measurement-to-noise ratio, for both pressure drop and temperature increase of the coolant, which would have been too low if liquid fluids had been used.

The experimental setup is equipped with standard instrumentation to allow the post processing of the data and to retrieve information on the temperature and pressure evolution of the coolants and the hot-gases. A list of the installed measuring sensors is presented in Tab.1.

Table 1 Measuring equipment.

N.	Type of sensor	Objective
94	Thermocouples Type T	Measure temperature of the chamber, the coolants and the propellants.
17	Pressure sensors WIKA A-10	Measure pressure in the chamber, and of the coolants in the manifolds.
3	Coriolis Mass flow meters	Measure mass-flow of GOx, CH4 and N2.
3	Dynamic pressure sensors	Monitor instabilities

On the AM specimen, pairs of thermocouples are placed at 6 azimuthal positions, with two different radial depths, to detect differences in the heat flux distribution around the circumference of the chamber. A gradient method is used whereby the local 1D heat flux is determined by examining the difference in temperature of two thermocouples placed at different radial depths. To grant stability in the measurement, the thermocouples are mounted with a spring-loaded system which assure the contact between the thermocouple and the wall at all times. Additionally, the implemented thermocouples were previously x-rays scanned, to determine the exact location of the sensible junction. Indeed, a minimum difference in the location of the measurement can lead to important variation in the post-processing, due to the strong temperature gradient, present near the hot-walls of rocket engines.

In addition, global heat flux is measured with a calorimetric approach: 4 thermocouples are placed respectively in the inlet and outlet manifold of the N₂ circuit, with a 90 degrees displacement, and their average is used to evaluate an inlet and outlet

temperature.

2.2. Test Matrix

The test campaign involves four different specimen whose geometry is the same. Different surface finish techniques have been applied on the hot surface and on the coolant side surface of each specimen. This results in four different combinations of surface roughness on the hot side and on the cold side. The nomenclature used in this paper for the conducted tests is shown in Tab.2., where “EDM” stands for “Electron-Discharge-Machining”. The second letter of the name of each specimen indicates the surface treatment of the combustion chamber, while the third letter refers to the cooling channels. The letter “M” is used for machined or EDM surfaces, which are smoother than the as-built surfaces, indicated with the letter “L”.

Table 2 Test specimens characteristics and nomenclature.

Test specimen	Hot-wall surface	Cooling channels surface
NMM	Machined	EDM
NML	Machined	As-built
NLM	As-built	EDM
NLL	As-built	As-built

A picture of the segment NLL is presented in Fig.2, to visualize the magnitude of the roughness under analysis. For each specimen, 5 loadpoints have been tested, which are summarized in Tab.3. Every loadpoint, presented in Tab.3, was run twice. Three levels of chamber pressure were tested to vary the amount of heat-flux. The mass flow of the coolant was also varied to vary the convection capabilities, thus the total heat pick up of the fluid.

Figure 2 Picture of the real hardware: focus on the surface roughness inside the combustion chamber.

Accordingly with the mass flow of nitrogen, the inlet pressure is adapted. In the case of $m_{N_2} = 1.2 \text{ kg/s}$, the inlet pressure is increased from 100 to 120 bar, to stay away from higher Mach numbers and avoid transonic effects ($Ma < 0.5$), while for $m_{N_2} = 0.8 \text{ kg/s}$, a relaxation of the inlet pressure was possible.

Table 3 Test Matrix.

Name	P_c [bar]	OF	m_{N_2} [kg/s]	P_{N_2} [bar]
REF	22.5	3.4	1.0	100
LP1	25	3.4	1.0	100
LP2	22.5	3.4	1.2	120
LP3	20	3.4	1.0	100
LP4	22.5	3.4	0.8	80

3. NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

In this work, RANS (Reynolds-Average-Navier-Stokes) simulations have been performed to compare numerical and experimental results. The goal is to assess the accuracy of the existing roughness model [2] developed to take into account the effects of surface roughness. This comparison is used to assess the accuracy of the model and tune the parameters relevant to predicting the enhancement of the friction factor and heat transfer. Conjugate heat transfer (CHT) numerical simulations have been performed by Sapienza University of Rome using an in-house code.

The implemented fluid solver is a preconditioned RANS flow solver, whose validation is reported in [18]. It is based on a Godunov-type finite volume method which is second order accurate in space and third in time [17]. Fluid thermodynamic properties are stored in a look-up table, thus, the solver is capable of dealing with any compressible fluid whose behaviour is described by a generic equation of state. Turbulence is computed according to the one-equation model of Spalart-Allmaras, equipped with the extension developed by Boeing to account for wall roughness [2]. The solver used for the solid domain is based on a 3D Fourier equation for the heat conduction in a solid material. It is a finite volume scheme and the solid properties are temperature dependent.

Numerical simulations pertaining to the experimental data from the "NML" test series described in the previous section are presented in this paper.

To analyse the friction increment due to roughness and the heat transfer enhancement, the roughness extension of the Spalart-Allmaras (SA) model, requires the equivalent sand grain roughness height h_s as input. This parameter has been evaluated from the experimental data, evaluating the pressure loss between inlet and outlet, and retrieving the corresponding sand-grain dimension from the Colebrook equation, [5].

To perform the simulations, the boundary conditions shown in Fig.3 are implemented, whose values were obtained through the averaging of the experimental data, as explained in the following section, and presented in Tab.4. The fluid computational grid is clustered towards the wall to properly solve the boundary layer.

Table 4 Boundary conditions of the numerical simulations

Test	A	B	C	D
m_{N_2} [kg/s]	0.92	0.77	1.18	1.09
\dot{q} [MW/m ²]	7	7.31	7.35	8.24

Figure 3 Simulation domain and implemented boundary conditions

4. RESULTS

4.1. Experimental results

The friction factor is calculated using the pressure data from the inlet and outlet manifold of the N_2 cooling circuit according to Eq. 1.

$$f = \Delta P \frac{2D_h}{\rho v^2 L} \quad (1)$$

The losses associated to the bend of the flow inside the manifolds have been taken into account, and evaluated as described in [3], before applying Eq.1

The analysis of the heat transfer requires several steps. The hot-gas wall temperature T_{hg} is determined by solving the 1D conduction problem between the measured value from the thermocouple to the hot-wall. Afterwards, the same methodology adopted in [23] is used for the estimation of the convection heat transfer coefficient. A logarithmic mean temperature difference is defined according to Eq. 2, and the heat flux using Eq.3. The convection heat transfer coefficient can then be evaluated as in Eq.4.

$$\Delta T_{LM} = \frac{T_{N_2,out} - T_{N_2,in}}{\ln[(T_w - T_{N_2,in}) / (T_w - T_{N_2,out})]} \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{q}_{N_2} = m_{N_2} c_p (T_{N_2,out} - T_{N_2,in}) / A_{hg} \quad (3)$$

$$h = \frac{\dot{q}_{N_2}}{\Delta T_{LM}} \quad (4)$$

where $T_{N_2,in}$ and $T_{N_2,out}$ are the inlet and outlet temperature of the nitrogen respectively at inlet and outlet, while T_w is an estimated wall temperature inside the combustion chamber. The results are then presented in terms of Nusselt number, Nu. Firstly, we present the resulting friction factor for

every tested coupon, in Fig.4. A value for h_s/D was extrapolated from the Colebrook equation, [5], by fitting the data points of each specimen.

Figure 4 Friction factor evaluated as in Eq. (1) from experimental data. Results from the Colebrook equation are added for comparison.

The corresponding relative roughness values for each test specimen are given in Fig.4. It is important to recall that the absolute roughness h_s used in the Colebrook equation is not the equivalent to the arithmetic average roughness height, Ra, or any other geometry-dependent parameter. Rather it is an apparent roughness that the fluid feels, according to Nikuradse original data, [14], which uses the sand grain diameter as absolute roughness value.

Important findings can be elaborated looking at Fig.4: as expected, the friction factor stays constant over a wide range of Reynolds number, being the flow fully turbulent. Little deviation is visible among the test points of the same test specimen, which are mostly due to the measurement accuracy, especially at lower Reynolds number, where the measured pressure difference become very small. In these conditions, the geometry and the real roughness of the test specimen play the most important role, shifting the curves up and down, as the roughness increases or decreases among the specimens. Additionally, the segments “NMM” and “NLM” whose cooling channels have been treated with EDM, present very similar results, proving that the post-processing of the surfaces is very repeatable, thus, gives the same performance. On the contrary, the segments “NLM” and “NLL”, whose cooling channels are left as-built, namely very rough, present very different friction factors. “NLM” has a flow resistance much higher than the segment “NLL”, presenting respectively a friction factor of around 0.185 and 0.111, Fig.4. Consequently, we observe two important outcomes: the friction resistance in the cooling channels increases greatly with respect to the smooth case, also presented with a black continuous line in Fig.4, both for the case of EDM post processing, and for channels which are left as built. However, for the production process and verification of the performances, it is of great

importance to notice that the additional post processing of the cooling channels (EDM in this case) gives a product with very repeatable performance.

The increase in heat pickup of the coolant in every specimen is highly influenced by the roughness features and has been found to be dependent on the friction factor increase. Norris et al. defined in [16] a correlation that links these two aspects, as given by Eq. (5)

$$\frac{Nu}{Nu_0} = \left(\frac{f}{f_0}\right)^n \quad (5)$$

with $n = 0.68Pr^{0.215}$ and where the subscript $_0$ refers to the smooth wall value. As a limitation to this correlation, the authors reported that the augmentation of Nu ceases for friction factor augmentation greater than 4.0. In this work, we want to assess the reliability of such an empirical approach in an extreme application domain, as the one of high-thrust rocket engine combustion chambers. In Fig.5, the calorimetric approach in Eq.3, is used to evaluate the heat flux in every segment of the chamber. To do so, the mass flow and the temperature difference of the coolant between the manifolds at the extremes of each segment are used, to evaluate a global heat flux on that segment. This approach leads to a step function, which is not the real distribution of the heat flux, but present the average heat flux that every segment has received. Every curve in Fig.5 presents the results for a different specimen, for one specific loadpoint, in particular the “REF” is presented, see Tab.3.

Figure 5 Comparison of Heat Flux among the different coupons, at the same operating point, “REF”, normalized with respect to the results of the segment NMM.

The data presented in Fig.5 are scaled with respect to the results obtained for the segment NMM (machined/EDM). Evidently, the segment “R” shows significant differences. The curves coming from the segments with a rough chamber (“NLM” and “NLL”) are evidently higher than the other two, which have a machined combustion chamber. Besides, with equal chamber surface quality, the roughness in the

cooling channels increases the heat flux, as visible comparing the segment “NMM” to “NML”, or the segment “NLM” to “NLL”. The variations of heat flux on the segments A and D are limited to less than 10% and can also be explained by the conduction effect between the segment R, which become quite hot due to the gaseous coolant. Additionally, small variations of combustion chamber pressure between different tests are also encountered, in the order of 1.3% P_c. On the other hand, the variation in heat flux on segment R is much larger, up to a difference of the 43 % between the segment NMM (smooth/EDM) and the segment NLL (rough/rough).

The heat flux results obtained from all the loadpoints and for all the specimen, are presented in Fig.6. In this case the results are scaled by the power law that best fit the results coming from the segment NMM.

As in Fig. 5, two markedly different groups can be distinguished: segments NMM and NML, with a turned combustion chamber, present a lower heat flux with respect to NLM and NLL, where the roughness on the hot-wall causes the heat flux to be much higher. Considering two segments with the same cooling channel surfaces, the increase in heat flux purely due to the different surface finish on the hot gas side can be evaluated. An increase of approximately 31-35% has been found from the results of the segment NLM when compared with the ones from the NMM, respectively presented in Fig.6 with grey triangles and orange squares. Same increase is obtained when comparing the other two segments, the NML and NLL, shown in Fig.6 with blue rhombuses and yellow crosses.

Figure 6 Heat flux as a function of the combustion chamber pressure, for the four tested coupons, scaled with respect to the power law fitting the results from NMM.

Additionally, the effect of the roughness in the cooling channels is very visible. When examining the results obtained for the segments NML and NMM, an increment of the heat flux can be noticed, due to the improved heat transfer performance of the coolant flowing over the rough surfaces of the cooling channels. The pickup of heat increases for

the NML segment by about 9-12% with respect to the NMM; furthermore, the same increment is visible between the other two segments, NLL and NLM.

Apart from the increase in heat transfer performances due to the roughness on the hot and cold sides, something else can be extracted from the interpolation of the results in Fig.6. If the data points are fitted, the heat flux results to be a power law of the combustion chamber pressure, a well-known fact that was firstly documented by Bartz in [4]. From his work, we can derive that in the portion of the combustion chamber where there is no area variation and the combustion can be considered completed, the convection heat transfer coefficient is function of $P_c^{0.8}$. This coefficient can be expressed as $h_{hg} = Q/A_{hg}(T_{hg} - T_w)$. Since the surface roughness increases the exchange area on the hot-gas side, A_{hg} , while the difference $T_{hg} - T_w$ decreases (because the hot-wall temperature increases), we can assume that these two effects balance the each other, and that the heat-pickup Q is still a function of the chamber pressure, as the convection coefficient h_{hg} . With this assumption in mind, Fig.6 shows how much the exponent of the power law changes, when made dimensionless with respect to the power-law fitting the data points of the segments NMM. This segment (smooth/EDM) can be interpolated with a power law with an exponent close to the theoretical one, used in the Bartz equation, [4]. Looking at the segment NML, thus adding surface roughness in the cooling channels, the exponent is lower than the one characterizing the segment NMM, resulting in a negative -0.15, when divided with respect the data of the reference specimen. This shows that the beneficial increment on heat transfer pickup given by the surface roughness in the channels tends to diminish when moving to higher combustion chamber pressures, or heat fluxes. Moving to the two segments with a rough chamber wall surface, the exponent is significantly increased for the NLM, and goes down again for the NLL. This result proves the remarkable influence that the surface quality has on the heat transfer performances of a rocket engine, and quantifies for the first time these effects, showing that a prediction based on a simple shift of the heat flux curve would not be accurate, and would lead to large errors if applied to a wide combustion chamber pressure range, due to the sensible change in the slope of these performance curves.

Although the heat pickup is significantly improved by the presence of surface roughness, the hot-wall temperature is sensibly higher as well, as mentioned above. Thus, for real engine applications, the two effects have to be cautiously balanced, because a too high temperature in the chamber might be obtained while trying to increase indefinitely the heat flux to the coolant.

4.2. Hot wall temperature

In this work T_w has been evaluated using a simplified 1D approach: the measurement of the closest thermocouple to the hot wall is considered, and defined T_m , and then a 1D conduction problem in the cylindrical combustion chamber is solved through Eq.6.

$$T_w = T_m + \frac{Q}{2\pi L \lambda} \ln(r_2/r_1) \quad (6)$$

where L is the length of the segment, λ is the thermal conductivity, Q is the absorbed heat, while r_1 and r_2 are the radial position of the hot wall and the thermocouple respectively. Additionally, to remove non-uniformity in the temperature distribution along the circumference of the chamber, the temperature T_m has been obtained by arithmetic average of the 6 thermocouples placed around the segment.

Figure 7 Ratio of the extrapolated hot-wall temperature over the bulk temperature difference of the coolant between outlet and inlet, as a function of the coolant mass flow, for the four tested coupons.

As explained in previous works, [7], the printing direction affects the distribution of the surface roughness in azimuthal direction, thus, affecting the temperature profile around the circumference of the specimen. Fig.7 presents the ratio between the predicted hot-wall temperature, and the temperature increase of the coolant.

The ratio that is being presented in Fig.7 can be seen as a performance parameter that indicates how much heat is picked from the walls and thus, absorbed by the fluid. The lower this index the better the heat transfer performances. The segment NLL shows the lowest ratio, since it features both a rough chamber and a rough cold gas side. On the contrary the segment NMM performs the worst among the four, having a smooth chamber and EDM cooling channels which do not have enhanced performance as in the rough case. The other two combinations stay more or less in the middle.

Besides, something else that can be noticed is that, once more, the distinction between smooth and rough combustion chamber influences the slope of the fitted curve. Indeed, if the data points are fitted

with a simple linear relation, it appears that the curves associated with NLM and NLL (featuring a rough chamber) are parallel, displaced by an approximately constant shift. The same happens to the other two curves, NML and NMM (smooth chamber surfaces), which appears to be parallel to the each other, but with a different slope with respect to the other couple. Once more, it is evident that the roughness can significantly influence the heat transfer performance with respect to the smooth case, and also change the expected behaviour of common performance indicators when predictions are performed on a wide range.

4.3. Nusselt number

The heat fluxes and the predicted hot-wall temperatures are used to evaluate the Nusselt number, as explained in Eq.2-4, following the same approach used in [23]. The results are presented in Fig.8. As already shown for the friction factor in Fig.4, the two specimen whose cooling channels have been treated with EDM (NMM and NLM) present repeatable performance, with the data from both specimens collapsing in one single curve. These curves however, are characterized by a lower Nusselt number, when compared with the results coming from NLM and NLL.

Figure 8 Nusselt number of the four specimens.

Indeed, NML and NLL present a Nusselt number variation with respect to the Reynolds number which seems to have a similar slope to the curves coming from NMM and NLM, but shifted upwards and reaching higher Nusselt number.

In particular, the segment with the highest friction factor, NML, also features the highest Nusselt number; even higher than the other specimen with as-built cooling channels. By using empirical laws to predict what the friction factor and the Nusselt number would have been in the same operating conditions but with smooth walls, the increase in pressure losses and heat transfer performance due to the surface roughness on the walls can be evaluated. To do so, the Colebrook equation is used to predict the smooth-wall friction factor, [5], and the Gnielinski equation for the corresponding Nusselt

number, [8].

The results are presented in Fig.9 for every specimen, along with the estimated Nusselt number increment that is obtained if the Norris correlation, in Eq.5, is fed with the real friction factor increment that has been found experimentally.

Figure 9 Heat transfer augmentation against friction augmentation of the four tested coupons.

First of all, the segments whose cooling channels have been treated with EDM demonstrate to be repeatable in terms of both friction factor and Nusselt number enhancement. On the other hand, the two segments with as-built cooling channels, NML and NLL, present different flow resistance and thus different heat transfer performances. However, apart from some spreading in the results, especially in the case of the NML segment (whose roughness seems to be more pronounced), the correlation from Norris fairly predict the results from these two specimens, and proves that the Nusselt number keeps increasing even for friction factor increment larger than 4.0, as was instead reported by Norris himself.

4.4. Numerical results

In this section, the numerical simulations results are presented. Four different test cases of the specimen “NML” have been simulated, see Tab.2. In order to save computational resources, only half of the cooling channel has been considered for the computations, and symmetry boundary conditions have been used to mirror the domain, see Fig. 3.

To match the experimental pressure drop obtained in the test campaign, the sand-grain parameter had to be properly tuned. Fig.10 shows the ratio between the relative roughness height h_s/D obtained by the Colebrook equation and the actual value imposed in the simulation.

For all the considered test cases, h_s/D has been increased of approximately 40% with respect to the value evaluated from the Colebrook law, to get the experimental pressure loss along the channel.

Figure 10 Relative roughness height h_s/D : ratio between CFD and Colebrook results.

Since the flow regime is fully rough, the friction factor value f should be independent from the Reynolds number, as also proven by the experiment, in Fig.4. Therefore, being the specimen the same, once h_s is calibrated for one of the test cases, it stays the same for the other.

Fig.11 shows the agreement between the numerical and experimental value, Eq.1 of the friction factor obtained once the equivalent sand grain roughness is calibrated.

Figure 11 Friction coefficient: ratio between CFD and experimental results.

Once the calibration is satisfactory, other physical quantities can be compared with the measurements obtained in the test campaign. Fig.12-13 show inlet static pressure p_{in} and outlet fluid temperature T_{out} respectively, as the ratio between the numerical and experimental results.

Figure 12 Inlet static pressure: ratio between CFD and experimental results.

The inlet static temperature and the exit static pressure are not shown since they have been imposed as boundary conditions.

Figure 13 Outlet fluid temperature: ratio between CFD and experimental results.

Obviously, the pressure agrees very well with the experimental values, as expected after the calibration of the sand-grain parameter. However, also the outlet temperature remarkably match the outlet temperature of the nitrogen measured during the tests, with an agreement within the 2%.

The procedure described in Section 5.1 has been adopted in order to compute the heat flux to be used as the hot gas side boundary condition in the CFD simulation, see Tab.2.

To compare numerical and experimental results, the measurement of the closest thermocouple to the hot wall T_m is considered (and its position is shown with a red symbol "P1" in Fig.14). Additionally, the hot gas side wall temperature T_w (blue symbol "P2" in Fig.14) derived through the 1D conduction problem in a cylindrical combustion chamber, Eq.6, is used for comparison.

Figure 14 Cooling channel section, independent axes for the sake of representation (not to scale). Red: thermocouple position, blue: reconstructed hot wall temperature position.

Fig. 15-16 show the ratio between the temperature obtained in the simulations in P1 and the reading of the thermocouple in the same position during the experiments. Despite the experimental data is an average between temperature at different azimuthal positions, simulation results are almost in line with the experiment, showing a maximum error up to 5%, which is also in line with the experimental accuracy that can be expected.

Figure 15 Thermocouple measured wall temperature: comparison between CFD and experiments.

Figure 16 Reconstructed hot gas side wall temperature: comparison between CFD and experiments.

Also, Fig.15 and Fig.16 do not show any difference, proving the validity of the one-dimensional conduction approach that has been used previously in this paper.

Figure 17 Nusselt number CFD numerical results.

Differently from the procedure explained in Eq. 2-4, CFD simulations allow to compute a local Nusselt number at every point of the domain, and then average the results. The Nusselt number has been computed as in Eq.6, and presented in Fig.17.

$$Nu = h_c D_h / k \quad (6)$$

where h_c is the coolant heat transfer coefficient, defined as $h_c = q_w / (T_w - T_b)$, in which T_b is the fluid bulk temperature, while q_w and T_w are the

average wall heat flux and wall temperature, respectively.

To complete this analysis, the nondimensional temperature field $\theta = (T - T_b)/(T_w - T_b)$ can be observed in Fig.18 at the outlet section of the channel.

Figure 18 Nondimensional temperature field θ , independent axes for the sake of representation (not to scale).

As it can be seen from the pronounced stratification, heat is being transferred mainly from the shorter side of the channel, close to the hot wall, but also conducted through the wall, and then redistributed through the other walls to the fluid by means of turbulent convection.

Temperature variations within the duct walls drive the temperature field in the fluid, which shows thermal stratification controlled by the temperature distribution along the rib walls.

5. CONCLUSION

3D printing processes are of high interest in the aerospace and space sector and understanding the fluid dynamics and heat transfer characteristics of channels produced with these techniques is of paramount importance in order to successfully operate the components in any kind of application. The study presented in this paper has investigated the effect of the surface roughness induced by a 3D printing process on the friction factor and heat flux of rectangular channels at operating conditions similar to real rocket engines.

The four specimens that have been tested granted a good comparison of the effects caused by the different surface quality characterizing the combustion chamber surface and/or the cooling channels surface. As expected, both the friction and the heat transfer have been enhanced with respect to the smooth case. However, this is the first study to give a quantitative measurement of such increase in a rocket application field. It has been found an increase of the heat flux up to the 12% for the cooling channels whose surfaces were not post-processed, compared with the channels that have been Electron-Discharge-Machined. The increase in heat flux goes up to 40% when repeating the comparison between the smooth (machined) and

the “as-built” combustion chamber surface.

What is even more interesting is that surface roughness is found to seemingly change the slope of well-known trends, such as the dependency between heat flux and chamber pressure. No precise numbers for this behaviour are given, since more data points would be needed to fit the curves with a higher degree of accuracy. Additionally, a deeper investigation has to be conducted on the azimuthal variation of the heat flux, caused by non-uniformity in surface roughness, due to the printing process angle. Destructive tests have to be performed to open the segments and locally measure the roughness profiles, to then compare the local temperature behaviour.

It has been proven that surface roughness can become a parameter in the design process which can help to achieve desired performances, based on the nature of the application. For example, increase the heat pickup of the coolant is now possible with rougher surfaces, paying however the price of a higher pressure drop.

The numerical simulations have shown that recently developed models can fairly predict the heat transfer mechanisms, if dedicated tuning of the sand-grain parameter is performed, which is usually possible only after the production and testing of the specimen.

The existing correlation from Norris has proven to be a good prediction also at friction factor augmentation higher than 4.0, however, with some margin.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The work was partly financed by the technology program MATRIKS-TOSCA by the German Space Agency, DLR, Bonn, under contract No.50RL2115.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] Aupoix, B. 2015. Improved heat transfer predictions on rough surfaces. *International Journal of Heat and Fluid Flow* 56, 160–171.
- [2] Aupoix, B. and P.R. Spalart. 2003. Extensions of the Spalart–Allmaras turbulence model to account for wall roughness. *International Journal of Heat and Fluid Flow* 24(4), 454–462.
- [3] Babcock and Wilcox Company. 1978. *Steam/ its generation and use*.
- [4] Bartz, R. D. 1965. Turbulent Boundary layer Heat Transfer from rapidly accelerating flow of rocket combustion gases and of heated air. *Advances in Heat Transfer* 2, 1–108.
- [5] Colebrook, C. F. 1939. Turbulent flow in pipes, with particular reference to the transition region between the smooth and rough pipe laws. *Journal of the Institution of Civil Engineers* 11,

- 133–156.
- [6] Cormier, Y., Dupuis, P., Farjam, A., Corbeil, A., and Jodoin, B. 2014. Additive Manufacturing of Pyramidal Pin Fins: Height and Fin Density Effects Under Forced Convection. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer* 75, 235–244.
- [7] Delgado, J., Ciurana, J., and Rodriguez, C. 2012. “Influence of Process Parameters on Part Quality and Mechanical Properties for DMLS and SLM With Iron-Based Materials. *International journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology* 60, 5-8, 601–610.
- [8] Gnielinski, V. 1976. New Equations for Heat and Mass Transfer in Turbulent Pipe and Channel Flow. *International Chemical Engineering* 16(2), 359–368.
- [9] Jones, J. O. C. 1976. An Improvement in the Calculation of Turbulent Friction in Rectangular Ducts. *ASME Journal of Fluids Engineering* 98, 173–180.
- [10] Latini, B., Fiore, M., and Nasuti, F. 2022. Modeling liquid rocket engine coolant flow and heat transfer in high roughness channels. *Aerospace Science and Technology* 126, 107672.
- [11] Mazzei, L., Da Soghe, R., and Bianchini, C., Eds. 2020. *CFD modelling strategies for the simulation of roughness effects on friction and heat transfer in additive manufactured components*.
- [12] Mazzei, L., Da Soghe, R., and Bianchini, C., Eds. 2021. *Calibration of a CFD methodology for the simulation of roughness effects on friction and heat transfer in additive manufactured components*.
- [13] Mazzei, L., Da Soghe, R., and Bianchini, C., Eds. 2022. *Calibration of a CFD methodology for the simulation of additively manufactured components accounting for the effects of diameter and printing direction on friction and heat transfer*.
- [14] Nikuradse, J. 1930. Untersuchungen über turbulente Strömungen in nicht kreisförmigen Röhren. *Ingenieur-Archiv* 1, 306–332.
- [15] Nikuradse, J. 1950. *Laws of flow in rough pipes*. NACA, Washington.
- [16] Norris, R. H. 1971. *Some Simple Approximate Heat Transfer Correlations for Turbulent Flows in Ducts with Surface Roughness*. American Society of Mechanical Engineering, New York, USA.
- [17] Pizzarelli, M., Nasuti, F., and Onofri, M. 2012. CFD analysis of transcritical methane in rocket engine cooling channels. *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids* 62, 79–87.
- [18] Pizzarelli, M., Nasuti, F., and Onofri, M. 2013. Coupled wall heat conduction and coolant flow analysis for liquid rocket engines. *Journal of Propulsion and Power* 29, 34–41.
- [19] Silvestri, S., Bauer, C., Lungu, P., and Haidn, O. 2018. Axial and Azimuthal Heat Load Distribution in a 7-Injector GOX-GCH₄ Combustion Chamber. *AIAA Joint Propulsion Conference*.
- [20] Silvestri, S., Celano, M., Schlieben, G., and Haidn, O., Eds. 2016. *Characterization of a Multi-Injector GOX-GCH₄ Combustion Chamber*.
- [21] Silvestri, S., Winter, F., Garulli, M., Celano, M., Schlieben, G., Haidn, O., and Knab, O., Eds. 2017. *Investigation on Recess Variation of a Shear Coax Injector in a GOX/GCH₄ Rectangular Combustion Chamber with Optical Access*.
- [22] Snyder, J. C., Stimpson, C. K., Thole, K. A., and Mongillo, D. 2015. Build Direction Effects on Flow and Heat Transfer for Additively Manufactured Channels. *ASME Journal of Turbomachinery* 138(5), 051006.
- [23] Stimpson, C. K., Snyder, J. C., Thole, K. A., and Mongillo, D. 2016. Roughness effects on flow and heat transfer for additively manufactured channels. *Journal of Turbomachinery* 138(5), 51008.
- [24] Stimpson, C. K., Snyder, J. C., Thole, K. A., and Mongillo, D. 2017. “Scaling roughness effects on pressure loss and heat transfer of additively manufactured channels. *Journal of Turbomachinery* 139(2), 21003.
- [25] Ventola, L., Robotti, F., Dialameh, M., Calignano, F., Manfredi, D., Chiavazzo, E., and Asinari, P. 2014. Rough Surfaces With Enhanced Heat Transfer for Electronics Cooling by Direct Metal Laser Sintering. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer* 75, 58–74.
- [26] Wong, M., Owen, I., Sutcliffe, C. J., and Puri, A. 2009. Convective Heat Transfer and Pressure Losses Across Novel Heat Sinks Fabricated by Selective Laser Melting. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer* 52, 281–288.